

Teachers' Service Conditions and Their Effectiveness in Ekiti State Secondary Schools

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Abstract:

There is a lot of emphasis on secondary education in Nigeria since it is the stepping stone between elementary school and college and experience has demonstrated that an employee's effectiveness is affected by his or her rapid and timely promotion. This study investigated the correlation between variables of conditions of service and teacher effectiveness in Ekiti secondary schools. The descriptive survey research design was adapted in the study. A total of 420 respondents were chosen from 20 public secondary schools in Ekiti State using proportional and purposive sampling technique. Conditions of Service Questionnaire" (CSQ) and was administered on the teachers and the second one tagged "Teachers' Effectiveness Questionnaire" (TEQ) were the self-designed questionnaires for the study. The instruments were screened by experts in educational management and others specialists in the fields of tests and measurement, to confirm their validity. The test re-test approach was used to assess the instruments' consistency. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to assess the data collected for the study. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed a significant relationship between salary and teacher effectiveness ($r\text{-cal } 0.632$ $p=0.000$), promotion and teacher's effectiveness ($r\text{-cal } 0.374$, $p=0.000$), and training and teacher effectiveness(0.436 , $P=0.000$). In conclusion, salary, promotion, training, and staff welfare were important variables contributing to teacher effectiveness. It was recommended among others that Governments at all levels should prioritise providing teachers with a welfare package since doing so will encourage them to give their all in the classroom, which will raise student achievement and teacher effectiveness.

Keywords: Teacher, Service Condition, Effectiveness, Secondary Schools,

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Introduction

There is a lot of emphasis on secondary education in Nigeria since it is the stepping stone between elementary school and college. The purpose of secondary education is to equip students with in-depth knowledge, foster their intellectual growth, and educate them so that they can contribute to national needs for highly educated human resources. Tertiary education, often known as post-secondary education, is the third and final stage of formal education. "Permanent literacy and numeracy development in children, effective communication ability development, training for further education and preparation for trades and crafts of the locality, good moral development, development of the basis for good physical health education, and development of the basis for scientific and reflective thinking" are all stated as major goals of secondary education in the National Policy of Education (2014).

A contract between an employer and an employee is called a "Conditions of Service." In order to utilise the service, the employee must consent to and agree to the terms of service. A condition of service may be a powerful tool for increasing productivity in the public sector. Condition of service is defined as that part of the employment process that establishes the duties, responsibilities, hours of work, salary, training, leaves, promotion, job security, entitlements, and other privileges to be enjoyed by a person employed; if all of these conditions of service are not met properly, it can become a poor condition of service.

The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014) outlines a number of goals that seem nearly impossible to achieve due to the inadequate execution of teachers' terms of service in secondary schools across the country. Teacher salaries must be paid on time and in full, teachers must be promoted based on merit and given their due, teachers must receive regular training, and schools must foster an environment that encourages teachers to give their all towards improving education's effectiveness.

The researcher noticed that certain secondary school instructors in Ekiti State no longer engage their pupils in engaging classes or maintain accurate records of their students' academic progress. Some educators don't seem to care if they show up to work on time, get along with their coworkers and students, show interest in the school's mission and initiatives, or do their jobs when they're assigned them. Conditions of service, leadership conduct, industrial activities, and ambiguity about roles all appear to have a role in how successful teachers are. Perhaps if secondary school teachers' conditions of service, such as salary, promotion, training, and teacher welfare, are effectively implemented and supervised, teacher effectiveness in secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria, will grow.

Salary, promotion, training, and staff conditions are all part of the terms of service. In common parlance, an employee's salary is their whole annual income, and this might include a number of different payments subject to different regulations. The federal government of Nigeria has standardised the salary of civil servants as set by the national salaries, income, and wages commission. According to Nagaraju and Pooja (2017), an argument made by Ivancevch and Glueck (2016), remuneration and benefits packages affect employee efficiency and effectiveness. Performance, comfort, and effectiveness are all improved. The effectiveness of workers, the quality of their job, and the number of hours they put in for the company might all improve if they were paid more.

Incentives are implemented for two main reasons. The primary objective is to inspire educators to work harder and longer hours. Teachers should devote more time to lesson preparation, extra-curricular coaching, and the development of innovative pedagogical

techniques in order to raise student achievement. Finding and hiring more competent educators is a secondary objective.

One motivation for working for a company is financial gain, in the form of increased compensation. From the employees' point of view, it is important that wages and salaries are fair, as stated by Agburu (2012): "for the significance of wages and salaries in Nigeria, wages should not only be ample, but they should also display various aspects of fairness." Whatever the situation may be, a lack of fair treatment and acceptable compensation or reward is sure to inflame the passions of the people who work for the company. Wages and pay are crucial to many workers in Nigeria. Life is quite precarious if one's salary is insufficient.

It cannot be overstated how important salary is. It has been suggested that financial incentives might help in job creation efforts. This is especially true in the developing world, where the needs of the majority of employees are not being satisfied from a physiological standpoint. Wages are a powerful incentive. It's crucial that salaries and wages be raised and that they be paid on time and in sufficient amounts. The salary of a teacher is the regular payment made to that person for services rendered. Wages and salaries paid to workers are important because, with money, teachers will be committed to attending classes for teaching regularly, attending morning assemblies regularly, and attending meetings regularly. In a situation where salary is contextually not adequately paid, teacher effectiveness in such a school would remain low.

It has been noticed that individuals are more devoted to their work when they are given promotions when they are deserving of them. This is likely because people appreciate and like receiving attention to their physical comfort and sense of self-worth. Experience has demonstrated that an employee's effectiveness is affected by his or her rapid and timely promotion. Hashemzadeh came to the conclusion that "the five aspects of management, education, motivation, participation, and quality of life impacted human force production." When an individual is refused promotion, there is no way to increase their effectiveness. It follows that a teacher's promotion is positively correlated with the degree to which she or he demonstrates enthusiasm for the school's mission, cares about its future, and works to strengthen ties between the institution and its surrounding neighbourhood.

Promotion can increase a teacher's effectiveness in completing their task quickly and voluntarily, according to the researcher and secondary school instructors. It'll inspire them to go above and beyond the call of duty. It has been found that some teachers are being denied promotions, others are not receiving their promotions, and investigations have uncovered cases where teachers were promoted to the next grade but are still being paid the salary for the previous grade. Teachers may grow disengaged from their work and leave their schools if they are not given opportunities for advancement (Muheeb, 2004). The need for advancement isn't the only thing that might motivate you to work hard to get a promotion; your pride could play a role, too. Therefore, if workers know that improving their performance will increase their chances of promotion, they will have little incentive to work effectively. However, it appears that when teachers are not promoted as and when due, they tend not to be motivated, resulting in low teacher effectiveness. This is because receiving an expected promotion at the correct time will increase the degree to which an employee is advised to perform his or her work successfully.

Human resource development (HRD) in the field of human resource management relies heavily on training. In order to do their jobs well, employees should have the skills, knowledge, attitudes, and techniques, as well as an appreciation for, and familiarity with, the

company's culture. Accurate training, together with timely staff growth and education, may yield significant benefits for the organisation in the form of increased productivity, understanding, loyalty, and engagement (Heathfield, 2012). Most often, new instructors don't have all they need to do a good job right away.

Teachers need ongoing professional development to acquire skills they lacked when they were hired, so that they can more effectively present lessons, explain concepts to students, hand out and grade assignments, require students to complete corrections, and make use of the latest in educational technology. In order for a school to train its teachers, it must do so for the reasons listed below (Beardwell & Holden, 1998). This is because new employees, while valuable resources, require training before they can perform their duties effectively or fit in with the rest of the staff. It's possible that the institution may launch new responsibilities and occupations, filling them with long-serving employees who will need retraining. These individuals alter their level of interest, knowledge, confidence, aspirations, and circumstances. There is a need for extra training since some employees may switch positions inside the institution based on endorsement or increase their expertise. In order to work together effectively, instructors must be creative. Management mandates development and education since the institution may want to be ready for a number of upcoming changes and want some teachers to develop "handy dexterities." This would entail the growth of the new supervisor's perspective, continual management training, managerial advancement, and the maturation of the aspiring senior staff.

Training is essential for companies that are serious about beating the competition or at least becoming the market leaders, as evidenced by Beardwell and Holden's (1998) arguments. The first stage entails employees being introduced to one another and the corporate culture. According to Ivancevich and Glueck (2016), training includes imparting knowledge, skills, and an appreciation of the organization's mission and goals to staff. As a result, staff members are better able to maintain their constructive engagement in the firm's goal attainment and exceptional instructor effectiveness thanks to training.

Training entails acquiring the know-how necessary to do a task successfully. Training may be used to directly enhance the work abilities of a person or a group by instructing them in more effective methods of doing their duties. Factory employees, for instance, could pick up on some basic bookkeeping skills that are useful on the job. Principals have access to many professional development opportunities, such as seminars, workshops, and refresher courses. There is no denying the significance of training in reaching the effectiveness goal. It also helps staff members keep up with the times and adapt to new ways of teaching. Oluchukwu (2000) writes that "training establishes a person as a revenue-generating institution that reaps the benefits of increased productivity."

A seminar, workshop, or conference is an educational discussion guided by an expert on a specific topic that lasts for many days. Formal gatherings of persons interested in the same topic are called seminars, workshops, and conferences. It's the same as an academic symposium, which brings together scholars with similar interests to share their findings and ideas through papers and presentations in scholarly journals. Seminars, workshops, and conferences provide teachers with chances for professional development, which appears to increase their effectiveness in the classroom.

A conference, in its widest meaning, is a meeting where people get together to talk about something. The most common kind of presentation is a paper followed by a Q&A session. There are several varieties of conferences. There are many different types of conferences

accessible, including academic conferences, business conferences, conference calls, news conferences, peace conferences, professional conferences, settlement conferences, and trade conferences.

According to their findings, the researcher has found that some secondary school teachers do not frequently attend most conferences sponsored by professional groups and other educational bodies. They may not be able to enrol since public secondary schools cannot provide them scholarships. The researcher also found that some instructors were dissuaded from applying for grants because of the difficulty in getting institutional bureaucracy to approve money for conferences and workshops.

Teachers' failure to frequently attend conferences has a detrimental impact on their effectiveness since it prevents them from learning new knowledge and developing the skills necessary to do their jobs. "When training is given in the form of a seminar or workshop in a helpful atmosphere, the result is that it boosts output, group work enhancement, greater worker adaptability, communication improvement, self-esteem, and collaboration, and each of these enhances the teacher effectiveness of teachers," writes Alabi (2012).

In most people's minds, a school's desire to invest in the professional growth of its teachers is directly proportional to that teacher's perceived effectiveness in the classroom. Teachers' effectiveness may be attributed, in part, to their exposure to professional development opportunities such as mentorship programmes, seminars, workshops, conferences, and continuing education courses. A low level of teacher effectiveness may be the result if these conditions are not met. Teachers, from what can be seen, do not appear to have the essential training to use the most up-to-date educational resources. Their effectiveness as educators tends to suffer as a result of this.

Human resources are undeniably crucial to every organisation, since they have complete command over its efficiency and effectiveness by calming any tremors caused by the company's interaction with the environment. Both monetary and non-monetary welfare facilities should be provided to management and staff by all firms. The success of any institution is largely dependent on its workforce, and the idea of the worker's welfare will always play a role in the effectiveness of any organisation.

Managers who are committed to employee growth and improvement may voluntarily offer these benefits as a sort of social welfare, or unions and governments may compel them to negotiate conditions for these perks. The researcher found that a good staff welfare package would attract a good calibre of teachers, which would increase their teacher effectiveness, justifying the focus on staff welfare programmes as a motivational strategy for teacher effectiveness.

It benefits everyone for employees to be invested in their work and feel appreciated. To ensure that their employees' welfare is taken care of, organisations must make various earnings available. A highly motivated welfare package in an organisation can boost teacher effectiveness, whereas a de-motivated welfare package typically has the opposite impact. Therefore, according to Waititu et al., (2017), businesses need to realise that a well-behaved employee is of significant advantage to them and provide them with enough welfare.

Therefore, staff welfare is inclusive, welcoming measures or circumstances offered by workers, union bodies, or other organisations to facilitate a positive work experience for individuals and their families. Whether private or public, the educational system should use welfare measures since doing so boosts morale, lessens risk and anxiety, eliminates yield and malingering, and increases creativity and work effectiveness. Therefore, a major step towards

accomplishing organisational goals would be to humanise the working life value by giving welfare amenities to employees. A teacher's welfare package, according to Igbogi (2018), improves teacher effectiveness.

The researcher has found little evidence of real concern for teachers' welfare, particularly with regard to their retirement benefits. There is a standard retirement age for teachers of sixty years of age or after thirty-five years of service. Sometimes teachers have to wait years to get their last gratuity, and in that time they may lose their jobs, get sick, or fall victim to fraud. The current administration has politicised the distribution of benefits like pensions and gratuities, making matters much worse. Teachers don't seem to have a choice in the health insurance they receive. If staff welfare isn't in place, teachers may lose interest in the school's mission and programmes, in working to strengthen ties between the institution and its surrounding community, in taking an active role in school events, in regularly teaching in their classrooms, in regularly attending morning assembly, and in going above and beyond in their regular work for the school. As a result, a lot of the teachers' time, effort, and focus is on figuring out how to implement plan B, which has a significant impact on teacher effectiveness. It is against this background that this study intends to investigate the correlation between variables of conditions of service and teacher effectiveness in Ekiti secondary schools.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated:

1. There is no significant relationship between salary and teacher effectiveness.
2. There is no significant relationship between promotion and teacher effectiveness.
3. There is no significant relationship between training and teacher effectiveness.
4. There is no significant relation between staff welfare and teacher effectiveness

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adapted in the study, the research design is descriptive because it entails collection of data in order to describe existing characteristics as they exist regarding conditions of service and teacher effectiveness. The population consisted of all teachers in and the public secondary schools in Ekiti State.

A total of 420 respondents were chosen from 20 public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The sample for the study were chosen using a multi-stage sampling procedure. In the first stage, a proportional stratified sampling technique was used to select 20 secondary schools in Ekiti State. The second stage involved the selection of 400 teachers based on the population of the teachers in each school that were sampled using proportional sampling technique. In the third stage, 20 principals from the selected secondary school were selected using a purposive sampling technique.

Two sets of self-designed questionnaires were utilized to collect data for this study. The first one is tagged "Conditions of Service Questionnaire" (CSQ) and was administered on the teachers. The second one tagged "Teachers' Effectiveness Questionnaire" (TEQ) which was administered on the principals. The Conditions of Service Questionnaire (CSQ) comprised two sections, A and B. Section A comprises items that would elicit information on the teachers' biographical information, while section B has 20 items that elicited information on the conditions of service. The questionnaire's items are rated on a four-point scale ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1).

The Teachers Effectiveness Questionnaire (TEQ) comprises three sections A, B and C Section. A contains items on the bio-data of the principal, Section B contains items on the bio-data of

the teacher to be assessed, Section C, on the other hand, has items that elicit information on teacher effectiveness. The items in the questionnaire are on a rating scale with four options ranging from Excellent to Poor: Excellent (4), Good (3), Fair (2), and Poor (1).

The instruments were screened by experts in educational management and others specialists in the fields of tests and measurement, to confirm their validity. The test re-test approach was used to assess the instruments' consistency. The Conditions of Service Questionnaire (CSQ) was administered twice within a period of two weeks on 20 Teachers public secondary schools that is not included in the sampled secondary schools for the study while the Teacher Effectiveness Questionnaire (TEQ) was administered on 2 principals to assess 20 teachers in 2 public secondary schools twice within an interval of two weeks. The reliability coefficients of the instruments were calculated by comparing the scores from the two sets of replies using Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis. The Conditions of Service Questionnaire (CSQ) had a reliability coefficient of 0.82, while the Teacher Effectiveness Questionnaire had a reliability coefficient of 0.74 (TEQ). The coefficients were deemed sufficient for reliability.

The researcher sought the permission of the secondary schools' authorities to administer the questionnaire on the respondents in the secondary schools to be sampled for the study. The researcher made follow-up visits that facilitate proper completion of the instruments where necessary. The researcher's personal visit to the secondary schools helped to reduce the difficulty of retrieving the instruments.

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to assess the data collected for the study. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between salary and teacher effectiveness

Table 1: Relationship between salary and secondary school teacher effectiveness

<i>Variables</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>r-cal</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Payment of salary	400	12.81	2.20		
Teacher effectiveness	400	57.62	9.54	0.632*	0.000

*P<0.05

Table 1 showed r-cal (0.632) is significant at 0.05 level of significance. The result is significant ($p < 0.05$) and the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there was significant relationship between salary and secondary school teacher effectiveness in Ekiti State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between promotion and teacher effectiveness

Table 2: Relationship between promotion and secondary school teacher effectiveness

<i>Variables</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>r-cal</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Promotion	400	11.72	2.16		
Teacher effectiveness	400	57.62	9.54	0.374*	0.000

*P<0.05

Table 2 showed r-cal (0.374) is significant at 0.05 level of significance. The result is significant ($p < 0.05$) and the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, there was significant relationship between promotion and secondary school teacher effectiveness in Ekiti State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between training and teacher effectiveness

Table 3: Relationship between training and secondary school teacher effectiveness

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-value
Training	400	12.19	2.08		
Teacher effectiveness	400	57.62	9.54	0.436*	0.000

*P<0.05

Table 3 showed r-cal (0.436) is significant at 0.05 level of significance. The result is significant ($p < 0.05$) and the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, there was significant relationship between training and secondary school teacher effectiveness in Ekiti State.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between staff welfare and teacher effectiveness.

Table 4: Relationship between staff welfare and secondary school teacher effectiveness

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-value
Staff welfare	400	12.43	1.81		
Teacher effectiveness	400	57.62	9.54	0.409*	0.000

*P<0.05

Table 4 showed r-cal (0.409) is significant at 0.05 level of significance. The result is significant ($p < 0.05$) and the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there was significant relationship between staff welfare and secondary school teacher effectiveness in Ekiti State.

Discussion

Teacher effectiveness was shown to be significantly correlated with salary, according to the research. This suggests that the appropriateness, fairness, and promptness with which their salary and other financial advantages are given to them may be related to the effectiveness of the instructor. When instructors are paid on time and in accordance with their contractual obligations, they show a high level of dedication to their profession. This conclusion may be due to the fact that instructors are motivated to continue working since they rely on their salary to meet their basic necessities. This result was consistent with the findings of Akande (2014), who found that staff instructor effectiveness was significantly correlated with the punctuality with which salary, fringe benefits, and other compensation were disbursed. However, the result disproved Ssali's (2011) assertion that there was no link between financial incentives and teacher effectiveness.

The study also found a strong correlation between promotion and teacher effectiveness in secondary schools. This suggests that the consistency, recognition, fairness, and breadth with which the merit system is followed in promoting teachers in the secondary school system are all directly connected to teachers' effectiveness. Possible explanations for this finding include the psychological and financial benefits of promotions for educators. This result supported the claims of Etejere et al. (2020) and Adedapo et al. (2020) that there was a strong relationship between promotion and secondary school teacher effectiveness and academic staff effectiveness, respectively.

Secondary school teachers' effectiveness was shown to be significantly correlated with their level of training. This strongly suggests that teacher effectiveness is linked to teachers'

exposure to various forms of professional development, such as seminars, conferences, workshops, and courses. Teachers' knowledge, expertise, and pedagogical abilities may all benefit from training, which may explain this conclusion. The results of this study corroborated those of Akinyele (2007), who found a strong correlation between teachers' levels of education and their effectiveness in the classroom.

The effectiveness of secondary school teachers was also shown to be significantly correlated with staff welfare. This suggested that a teacher's health, other benefits, and the adequacy of their insurance coverage are related to how seriously their welfare is taken, as well as how consistently and persistently they discharge their stationary duties to students and the school community. The extrinsic motivating rewards that this kind of welfare service provides to the educator could account for this. Doucouliagos and Larecho (2003) discovered a positive correlation between employer satisfaction and effectiveness, which is supported by this finding.

Conclusion

This study concluded that salary, promotion, training, and staff welfare were important variables contributing to teacher effectiveness.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. There has to be an increase in teachers' salary and other allowances from the federal and state governments. In order to promote greater teacher effectiveness, make sure that teacher pay are regularly reviewed to reflect the current status of the economy.
2. It is the responsibility of the government and the principals of secondary schools to promote teachers who satisfy the requirements for promotion promptly and on the basis of merit.
3. The government and secondary school principals should keep providing and funding professional development opportunities for teachers in the form of workshops, seminars, and conferences to help them become more proficient in the use of cutting-edge pedagogical resources and more engaging communicators of academic content.
4. Governments at all levels should prioritise providing teachers with a welfare package since doing so will encourage them to give their all in the classroom, which will raise student achievement and teacher effectiveness.

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